

Synthesis of Chromones. Part III. Condensation of β -Naphthol with Alkyl Acetoacetic Esters.

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The condensation of phenols with β -ketonic esters in presence of sulphuric acid (Pechmann reaction) and in presence of phosphorus pentoxide (Simonis reaction) has been the subject of investigation by the author (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 129, 407, 619; 1932, 9, 25, 31) and discussion, excepting a generalisation (*ibid.*, 1932, 9, 32) regarding these reactions was postponed, until the accumulation of further experimental data. In the meantime, Robertson and his collaborators (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 1256, 1877, 2426; 1932, 1180, 1681) arrived at the conclusion that the Simonis reaction depends entirely on the nature of the phenol and is independent of the nature of the ester; which view was afterwards discarded by the same authors (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 1180). While studying the β -naphthopyrones, Dey and Lakshminarayanan (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 153) have supported the earlier view of Robertson and others that "The important factor, which determines the course of the condensation, however, is obviously not the β -ketonic ester but the phenol itself, as suggested by Robertson."

That the course of these reactions, however, depends on *both* the phenol and the β -ketonic ester, is shown by the following experimental facts.

Esters.	Products with H_2SO_4 .	Products with P_2O_5 .
	<i>with β-naphthol.</i>	
Ethyl acetoacetate	Mixture of coumarin and chromone (Dey and Lakshminarayanan, <i>loc. cit.</i>).	Chromone (Dey and Lakshminarayanan, <i>loc. cit.</i>).
Ethyl α -methylacetoacetate	Coumarin in poor yield*	Chromone *
Ethyl α -ethyl (or α -propyl or α -isopropyl)-acetoacetate	No reaction*	Chromones *

* *vide infra.*

Esters.	Products with H ₂ SO ₄ . with m-cresol.	Products with P ₂ O ₅ .
Ethyl acetoacetate	Coumarin (Fries and Klostermann <i>Ber.</i> , 1906, 39, 971).	Coumarin (Chakravarti <i>J. Indian Chem. Soc.</i> , 1932, 9, 26; Robertson and others, <i>J. Chem. Soc.</i> , 1932, 1681).
Ethyl α-methylacetoacetate	Coumarin in poor yield (Fries and Klostermann, <i>Annalen</i> , 1908, 362, 3).	Chromone (Petschek and Simonis, <i>Ber.</i> , 1913, 46, 2014).
Ethyl α-propyl (or α-iso-propyl or α-isobutyl)-acetoacetate	No reaction (Chakravarti, <i>J. Indian Chem. Soc.</i> , 1932, 9, 32).	No product can be isolated from the reaction mixture.
with p-cresol.		
Ethyl acetoacetate	Coumarin (Pechmann and Cohen, <i>Ber.</i> 1884, 17, 2187).	Coumarin (Robertson and Sandrock, <i>J. Chem. Soc.</i> , 1932, 1480).
Ethyl α-methylacetoacetate	Coumarin (Chakravarti, <i>J. Indian Chem. Soc.</i> , 1932, 9, 29).	Chromone (Petschek and Simonis, <i>loc. cit.</i>).
Ethyl α-ethylacetoacetate	Coumarin in poor yield (Robertson and Sandrock, <i>loc. cit.</i>).	Chromone (Robertson and Sandrock, <i>loc. cit.</i>).
Ethyl α-propyl (or isopropyl) acetoacetate	No reaction (Chakravarti, <i>J. Indian Chem. Soc.</i> , 1932, 9, 31).	No product can be isolated from the reaction mixture.
Ethyl α-chloroacetoacetate	Coumarin	Coumarin (Robertson and Sandrock, <i>loc. cit.</i>).

The present paper describes the β-naphthapyrones prepared by the condensation of β-naphthol with alkyl acetoacetic esters. The β-naphthachromones are characterised by the formation of 2-styryl derivatives, which distinguish them from the isomeric coumarins (*cf.* Chakravarti, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 181). The generalisation, previously recorded, holds in this case also. β-Naphthol does not react readily with acetoacetic ester in presence of sulphuric acid to form coumarins, and it forms chromones in comparatively good yield in presence of phosphorus pentoxide.

The condensation of phenols with other β-ketonic esters. *e.g.*, acetone dicarboxylic ester, oxalacetic ester, benzoylacetic ester and acetosuccinic ester, in presence of phosphorus pentoxide is being studied and the results will be communicated shortly.

EXPERIMENTAL.*

3:4-Dimethyl-1:2-β-naphthapyrone.—A mixture of β-naphthol (5 g.) and ethyl α-methylacetoacetate (5 g.) was slowly added to ice-cold concentrated sulphuric acid (12 c.c.) and the solution was shaken. The solution was kept for 48 hours and crushed ice added to it; only a small amount of solid separated on standing. This was crystallised from dilute alcohol as colourless needles, m.p. 127°. (Found: C, 80.12; H, 5.53. $C_{15}H_{12}O_2$ requires C, 80.35; H, 5.35 per cent.).

2:3-Dimethyl-1:4-β-naphthapyrone.—To a warm solution of β-naphthol (10 g.) and ethyl α-methylacetoacetate (10 g.), phosphorus pentoxide (25 g.) was gradually added and the mass shaken. The mass became hot and on standing for 15 minutes, it was heated on the water-bath for about 1 hour. Crushed ice was then added and the thick oil treated with cold caustic soda solution, when solid separated. It was thoroughly washed with water, dried and crystallised from rectified spirit in colourless plates, m. p. 180° (mixed with the coumarin, m. p. 95°). (Found: C, 80.22; H, 5.41. $C_{15}H_{12}O_2$ requires C, 80.35; H, 5.35 per cent.).

2-Styryl-3-methyl-1:4-β-naphthapyrone.—A solution of 2:3-dimethyl-1:4-β-naphthapyrone (1 g.) in absolute alcohol was treated with alcoholic sodium ethoxide (0.5g. sodium) and benzaldehyde (1g.), when only a slight yellow colouration was produced. The solution, on keeping overnight, deposited yellow crystals, which were filtered off, washed with dilute alcohol and recrystallised from absolute alcohol in long yellowish silky needles, m. p. 186°. (Found: C, 84.32; H, 4.91. $C_{22}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 84.6; H, 5.12 per cent.).

The 3:4-dimethyl-1:2-β-naphthapyrone, prepared with sulphuric acid, does not react with benzaldehyde.

2-Methyl-3-ethyl-1:4-β-naphthapyrone was prepared from β-naphthol and ethyl α-ethylacetoacetate in presence of phosphorus pentoxide and isolated in the manner described above. It crystallised from dilute alcohol in colourless plates, m. p. 117°. (Found: C, 80.22; H, 5.95. $C_{16}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 80.67; H, 5.88 per cent.).

2-Styryl-3-ethyl-1:4-β-naphthapyrone was prepared by condensing the above pyrone with benzaldehyde as usual. It crystallised in yellowish silky needles from absolute alcohol, m. p. 183°.

* The β-naphthapyrones have been named according to Dey and Lakshminarayana (loc. cit.).

(Found: C, 84.35; H, 5.32. $C_{23}H_{18}O_2$ requires C, 84.66; H, 5.51 per cent.).

2-Methyl-3-propyl-1:4-β-naphthapyrone, the condensation product of β-naphthol and ethyl α-propylacetoacetate in presence of phosphorus pentoxide, crystallised from rectified spirit as colourless needles, m. p. 95°. (Found: C, 81.12; H, 6.1. $C_{17}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 80.95; H, 6.35 per cent.).

2-Styryl-3-propyl-1:4-β-naphthapyrone crystallised from rectified spirit in yellow silky needles, m. p. 168°. (Found: C, 84.35; H, 5.98. $C_{24}H_{20}O_2$ requires C, 84.70; H, 5.88 per cent.).

2-Methyl-3-isopropyl-1:4-β-naphthapyrone was prepared by condensing β-naphthol and ethyl α-isopropylacetoacetate in presence of phosphorus pentoxide. It crystallised from rectified spirit in colourless prismatic needles m. p. 131°. (Found: C, 80.83; H, 6.43. $C_{17}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 80.95; H, 6.35 per cent.).

2-Styryl-3-isopropyl-1:4-β-naphthapyrone crystallised from rectified spirit as silky yellow needles, m. p. 187°. (Found: C, 84.53; H, 5.67. $C_{24}H_{20}O_2$ requires C, 84.70; H, 5.88 per cent.).

β-Naphthol does not condense with ethyl α-ethyl (or α-propyl or α-isopropyl)-acetoacetate in presence of sulphuric acid.

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